

EXFOLIATION AND DISPERSION OF MXENE IN EPOXY RESIN USING DISPERSING AGENTS AND THREE-ROLL MILLING

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- MXenes, a rapidly emerging class of 2D transition metal carbides, nitrides, and carbonitrides, possess a unique layered structure.
- Their outstanding electrical conductivity, large surface area and controllable surface chemistry make them ideal for the production of advanced composites.

Polarity Mismatch

Polar functional groups hinder dispersion of MXene in polymer matrices, leading to agglomeration and limiting broader application.

Dispersion-driven performance

Insufficient dispersion limits performance in advanced composites (e.g., EMI shielding, electrical conductivity).

Need for effective methods to achieve homogeneous dispersion.

- To identify the most effective dispersant for achieving homogeneous dispersion of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene powder in an epoxy resin matrix, and to evaluate the performance of three-roll milling techniques in facilitating uniform MXene distribution.

Dispersing Agents

Surfactants and copolymers reduce surface tension and provide steric or electrostatic repulsion, preventing MXene aggregation.

Three-Roll Milling

Applying high shear forces effectively exfoliates and disperses 2D nanoparticles within the polymer matrix.

- **MXene $Ti_3C_2T_x$** (Laizhou Kai Kai Ceramic Materials Co., Ltd, Shandong Province, China)
- **CHS-EPOXY® 520 Bisphenol-A-based epoxy resin** (Spolchemie Company, Czech Republic)
- **Curing agent - Jeffamine D230:Jeffamine D2000 4:1** (Huntsman Corporation, The Woodlands, TX, USA)
- **Dispersants - DISPERBYK-180 and BYK-9076** (BYK-Chemie GmbH, Wesel, Germany)

Introducing Steric Dispersing Agents

- **DISPERBYK-180** is a hydroxy-functional carboxylic acid ester with particles-affinic groups.
- **DISPERBYK-180** deflocculates particles by means of steric stabilization. As a result of the small particle sizes can be achieved.

Introducing Steric Dispersing Agents

- **BYK-9076** is an alkylammonium salt of a high molecular weight copolymer containing amine groups and carboxylic functionalities.
- **BYK-9076** separate particles by means of **steric stabilization**. It also generates a uniform electrical charge in the particles (**electrostatic stabilization**). The resulting repulsion effect and the steric stabilization prevent any aggregation.

Preparation of MXene/Epoxy Films

MXene Distribution in Epoxy Matrix

Without Dispersant

With BYK-9076

With DISPERBYK-180

MXene Distribution in Epoxy Matrix

The Structural Properties of MXene/Epoxy Composites

XRD Patterns of MXene/Epoxy Composites

The reduced intensity and broadening of the (002) peak at 8° in XRD patterns indicate improved exfoliation of MXene layers.

Tensile Testing Parameters

- **Equipment:** Testing Machine (Admel Lhomargy, France)
- **Load Cell:** 100 N
- **Crosshead Speed:** 1 mm/min
- **Gauge Length:** 22 mm.

- Effective exfoliation and homogeneous dispersion of MXene in epoxy resin were achieved through a synergistic approach combining dispersing agents with high-shear three-roll milling.
- The use of dispersants and high-shear three-roll milling ensured a uniform distribution of exfoliated MXene throughout the epoxy matrix, minimising agglomeration.
- BYK-9076 acts as an effective dispersant and compatibiliser for MXenes in an epoxy matrix. It can also be used to functionalise the MXene surface, enhancing compatibility with the polymer matrix and improving the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite.

Thank you for your attention

